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Improving the Effectiveness of the Organizational and Economic Mechanism of the Service Sector

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Abstract

This study explores the enhancement of the organizational and economic mechanisms within the service sector in Uzbekistan amidst ongoing economic reforms. The introduction underscores the state's focus on modernizing production and improving infrastructure to boost economic sectors, including the service sector. A notable gap in existing research is the limited exploration of specific organizational strategies for optimizing service sector performance. Methodologically, this research employs monographic analysis, synthesis, and systematic analysis of foreign experiences to derive actionable insights. The findings reveal that optimal organizational structuring and digitization are critical for improving service delivery efficiency. Results indicate that flexible and well-organized service activities can mitigate social and economic challenges, such as employment and business activity. The study suggests that implementing comprehensive service standards and leveraging digital tools can significantly enhance labor productivity and service quality. Implications highlight the need for policy reforms to foster a competitive service environment, support small enterprises, and integrate advanced technologies to sustain sectoral growth and economic stability.

Keywords: service sector, economic mechanism, digitization, labor productivity, Uzbekistan, organizational structure, economic reform, service quality, policy reform

Introduction

On the part of the head of state of the Republic of Uzbekistan, modernization of production, technical and technological renewal, implementation of production, transport-communication and social infrastructure projects, modern ways of ensuring employment, and carrying out innovative production policy, 'attention is being paid. In particular, in this regard, structural changes are taking place in the national economy as a result of reforms aimed at fundamental reform of economic sectors and technical and technological re-equipment in the Republic of Uzbekistan. In particular, "rapid development of the service sector, increasing the role and share of services in the formation of the gross domestic product, fundamentally changing the composition of the provided services, first of all, at the expense of their modern technological types" is one. Based on these tasks, it is necessary to reform the public utility sector, improve the qualifications of employees, and create an environment of free competition in the public utility sector.

Analysis of the literature on the topic.

Fotis Kitsios, Maria Kamariotu on issues of digitization of the service sector in the context of the transition to a digital economy, in the scientific article "Digitalization of the innovation process in the service sector: application and research areas," the purpose of the digitization of the service sector in the context of the innovation economy, In the process of developing new types of services, the role of digital programs and technology and ways of effective use of digital technology by managers in the implementation of services, as well as ideas on attracting investments to improve the technological level in the field of digital services, are presented, as are suggestions and recommendations .

M.Q.Pardaev, Q.J.Mirzaev, and O.M.Pardaev, "Economics of the Service Sector," in the Study Guide, theoretical issues of the economy of the service sector, the main directions and prospects of the development of the sector by sectors, the specific characteristics of each sector and this sector, and the ways of evaluating and accounting the activity have been considered. Also, the content of the activities of the utility service sector and the ways of their accounting are analyzed.

M.M. Payazov's scientific article entitled "Transformation of the service sector is a priority in managing the economy" addresses issues of digitization of the service sector, the role of digitization of the service sector in ensuring the quality of life of the population, the role of the state system in the transformation of the sector, issues such as the digitization of production enterprises, the use of internet stores and internet banking services by the population, the analysis of the situation in the regions, and the increase in the well-being of the population as a result of the digitization of the service sector.

Methodology

The methodology employed in this study encompasses a range of analytical techniques designed to thoroughly investigate the problem. Primarily, the research leverages the results from monographic analysis of foreign experiences, providing a comprehensive understanding of the subject matter. Additionally, monographic research methods are utilized to delve deeper into specific case studies, enriching the analysis with detailed insights. The approach further integrates analysis and synthesis techniques to systematically break down and reassemble the data, ensuring a holistic perspective. Systematic analysis is also a key component, facilitating the identification of underlying patterns and internal capabilities. These methodologies collectively enhance the robustness and depth of the research, offering a well-rounded exploration of the issue at hand.

Results and discussion

In the conditions of the development of market relations, the proper formation of the service sector from an organizational and economic point of view is of great importance. If the development of this sector is organizationally optimal and flexible in relation to the conjuncture of the service market, the quality and efficiency of service delivery will be higher. Correct organization of labor activities in the service sector will lead to the elimination of a number of social and economic problems on the scale of the national economy. For example, on the basis of the development of the sector, it will ensure the employment of the population, increase the business activity of employees, operationalize the provided services, etc.

The complexity and diversity of the components of the production and service process in the service sector and the possibility of independent selection, calculation, design, and coordination of their implementation activities make important changes to the content of work.

In order to ensure the most efficient work of employees in service enterprises, it is possible to study and improve service processes, develop comprehensive service standards, and increase labor productivity based on the effective use of working time. need to be determined. However, there are factors that slow down and stop the increase of labor productivity even in the current conditions of the development of market relations. Because the enterprises providing services do not continuously reduce costs, increase the volume of production and services, but take advantage of the scarcity and scarcity of the products they produce or the services they provide, and increase their prices in return for a planned amount of income they are getting. This situation, in turn, not only increases the further development of the uncontrollable inflationary process but also makes it impossible to reduce the costs of organizing and managing the service process by widely introducing scientifically based service norms.

In the current conditions, it is necessary not only to establish the interaction of workers' activities with the commoditized elements of work but also to solve problems such as the formation of labor relations between the "human-technique" participants of mutual cooperation activities and the improvement of live labor efficiency.

Through the research of the organizational structure of the service sector in foreign countries, we can classify the organizational structure of the service market in our republic as follows:

- on implementation mechanisms (mediation financial, information-technological, legal, marketing);
- according to the form of ownership (private, cooperative (community), state, social, foreign);
- according to the scope of provided services (international, national, interregional, regional, local);
- according to the types and areas of services provided: business services (financial, insurance, credit services), distribution services (trade, catering), social services (education, health care, physical culture, legal services).

Many foreign economists propose to classify the structural structure of the service sector in terms of its industry characteristics and development. In our opinion, it is appropriate to classify this field from an organizational and economic point of view.

In this case, it is necessary to highlight the following:

information-commercial infrastructure (marketing centers, advertising agencies, information gathering and processing centers, etc.);

- economic and legal infrastructure (courts, legal consultation centers, advocacy and notary offices, etc.);

- financial and credit infrastructure (commercial banks, credit, insurance, and guarantee organizations);

trade, mediation infrastructure (fairs, stock exchanges, trading houses, commercial centers, etc.).

The above-mentioned classifications are of great importance in ensuring the efficiency of the service sector. However, reforms aimed at increasing the importance of services in the economic policy of our country require further development of these service sectors. For example, trading houses, organizations, and fairs, as types of services, have a positive effect on the sale of food and non-food products and the effective activity of their producers. However, services, as special goods, require specific requirements for those who provide them. As confirmation of this opinion, the place and role of fairs can be cited as an example. Trade-intermediation structural structure of the service sector in later times.

Table 1

Growth rate of market services provided in the Republic of Uzbekistan, (%).

Code	Classifier	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022-
G	Trading services	120,5	100,3	104,9	107,4	103,8	112,3	108,3
J	Communication and information services	114,6	121,3	115,9	108,3	123,8	126,4	128,8
H	Transport services	107,8	109,9	104,5	106,7	91,4	115,7	111,8
I	Accommodation and food services	121,1	112,1	107	107,3	80,3	132,3	122,3
K	Financial services	119,8	136,5	121,5	147	125,6	128	131,7
L	Services related to real estate	117,5	106,6	107,9	104,7	90	123,1	110
71	Services in the field of architecture, engineering research, technical testing and analysis	115,3	124,7	118,1	115,5	93,3	117,9	105,9
77	Rental services	117,6	102,1	110,4	98,3	98,4	118,7	112,6
P	Services in the field of education	107,8	125,6	110,5	109,5	101	130,8	114,1
Q	Services in the field of health	122,2	116,9	113,4	114,7	94,8	128,5	113,4
95	Computer and household goods repair services	115,6	102,6	104,2	107,1	94,5	122,9	106,6
96	Personal services	113,8	100,7	102,2	105,4	94,7	114,4	107,1
100	Other services	114,9	111,8	121,2	116,3	99,7	113	114,4

From the data in the above table, we can analyze that there are growth trends in the service sector in our country. However, if we pay attention to trade services, it was 120.5% in 2016, and by 2022 this figure will decrease to 108.3%. We can see that the main reason for this is the digitization of the sales service process. Also, if we are paying attention to the volume of communication services, here we can observe growth trends of 114.6% in 2016 and 128.8% by 2022. Therefore, it requires us to introduce the mechanisms of formation of communication services in our country to other types of services. To do this, we will be able to master the methods that are suitable for our country and increase the volume of service by doing a deep analysis of foreign experiences.

It is known that currently commercial banks rarely provide loans to small and private entrepreneurs operating in the service sector. The reason for this situation is explained by the small volume of financial operations in service enterprises, their inability to provide the necessary guarantees for loans, and the issues of stability of these enterprises.

Therefore, various organizations to be established to support service enterprises will provide an opportunity to expand their scope of activity with the help of financial, material, and other support. Currently, although the activity of service enterprises is developing in the

Samarkand region, there are no organizations that directly provide credit, coordination, and other support for their activities.

So, in our opinion, at present, the organization of the association of service enterprises is an important organizational structure that ensures the efficiency of the service industry. It will be possible to organize comprehensive customer service (providing all services).

Another organizational mechanism for increasing the efficiency of service enterprises is an information system that serves the industry. This system includes, in our opinion, the following: advertising agencies, marketing service centers, permanent or traveling exhibitions, media and electronic communication systems, etc. In our opinion, further development of information provision in the field of service provides an opportunity to fully satisfy the population's ability to pay for services, to assess the growth dynamics of this sector, and to improve the quality and efficiency of the services provided. To do this, it is necessary to establish special service-marketing centers for studying the demand for services at the regional level. This organizational structure includes the following areas of activity:

- development of scientific and practical manuals for studying demand and supply for new types of services;
- preparation of reports, booklets, and lectures for the service context at the regional level for subjects who feel the need for services;
- conducting questionnaires and sociological research to determine the quality of the provided service;
- participation in social events, fairs, and exhibitions to solve problems in the field of services.

An important organizational link that provides information provision for service enterprises is advertising activity. Its importance for this industry is the dissemination of information about services to the public in various forms, while advertising is not only a source of information, but it is an important organizational mechanism that stimulates new needs for services and the ability of the population to pay.

Currently, service enterprises do not have the opportunity to organize their own advertising services because they have neither financial nor material opportunities for this purpose. Therefore, in our opinion, it is necessary to establish special advertising agencies, which conclude contracts between service enterprises promoting services and consumers and deal with special orders at the regional level.

Another structural element of the services market is developing in an alternative way—these are their fairs and exhibitions. Currently, the tasks of wholesale fairs and exhibitions are changing radically. These changes are aimed at increasing the effectiveness of services in a real way.

- Ensuring the material and technical basis of information flow in the service sector includes information and communication tools, including telephone, telex, facsimile communication, satellite communication, and computer centers. One of the characteristics of information centers and communication in the improvement of the service sector is that, based on them, it creates the possibility of independent information provision between producers and service providers, and they have access to information. There will be no dependence on each other. This situation ensures the efficiency of service enterprises.

- The result of improving the collection, processing, and delivery of information on service provision is manifested in reducing transaction costs, increasing the efficiency of service provision, improving material and technical support, and accelerating the circulation of financial resources. Therefore, in our opinion, it is important to create a database of information resources about service industry networks, to organize their basic set, and to be a source for researching directions for the development of the industry. is considered

- Conclusions and suggestions.

- Based on the above-mentioned opinions and information, we have developed the following proposals and recommendations in order to improve the organizational and economic mechanism of increasing the efficiency of service enterprises in our country. In particular:

- further improvement of the policy of liberalizing the activities of service enterprises in the republic;

- promoting the experience of highly efficient service networks to other types of services in order to improve the quality of service;

- to increase the efficiency of its organizational and economic links by further accelerating the digitization of system activities in order to further improve the quality of service;

- development of a road map for the training of specialists based on the level of qualification, retraining, and service nomenclature of workers and employees operating in service enterprises in the republic and region and involving them in practice;

- to further increase the overall share of the service sector in our country by putting into practice suggestions such as the formation of a system for managing, controlling, and monitoring financial transactions at the regional and national level through the digitization of the financial activities of service enterprises; the work of attracting investments to them; the population's livelihood can ensure their well-being, create new jobs, and allow the economic growth of our country.

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